

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

OBTAINING THE MOST VALUABLE INBRED SILKWORM LINES BY COMBINATIONAL ABILITY

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Abstract

Obtaining the most valuable inbred lines in terms of combinational ability is of particular interest in silkworm breeding, because it is by this method that breeders derive the most outstanding breeding material for hybridization. In order to create highly heterotic inbred lines, it is necessary to apply strict selection of inbred lines for viability. As part of the research, four inbred lines F-1, F-2, F-3, F-4 with plus and minus selection for caterpillar viability were obtained from large cocoon breeding lines L-51 and L-48. The increasing effect of heterosis of topcrosses, bottomcrosses and incrosses originating from inbred lines, starting from J_4 to J_6 , indicates the constant formation of high combinational ability as the breeding effect increases on increased and decreased viability of caterpillars

Keywords: silkworm, eggs of the silkworm, caterpillar, cocoon, butterfly, translocation, female, male, sex regulation, chromosome, genetic engineering.

Introduction

Heterosis is widely used in agriculture and brings a huge economic effect, but the reason for its manifestation has not yet been fully disclosed.

The well-known hypotheses of dominance, overdomination, and genetic balance do not give a complete answer to the question of what causes when crossing certain inbred lines, not only lead to the restoration of traits depressed during inbreeding to the level of the original freely crossing parental forms, but also in some cases to a significant increase in this level. Meanwhile, obtaining the most valuable inbred lines in terms of combinational ability is of particular interest, because it is in this way that breeders derive the most outstanding breeding material for hybridization.

Based on numerous experiments, V.A. Strunnikov proposed a new hypothesis for the occurrence of heterosis [1]. Based on the concept of the formation of combinational ability put forward by him, based on the emergence of compensatory gene complexes and the study of the nature of heterosis, it was possible to develop targeted methods of selection for combinational ability in mulberry silkworms and confirmed drosophila, barley and peas.

One of these methods is selection against the background of inbreeding. In order to create highly heterotic inbred lines, it is necessary, according to the concept of V.A. Strunnikov, to apply a strict selection of inbred lines for viability. The effect of such selection can be verified by further study of heterosis in various related and unrelated crosses. The most useful and weighty in the sense of evidence are crosses of inbred lines with their original breeds: top crosses (breed x inbred line), bottom crosses (inbred line x breed), and incrosses (inbred line 1 x inbred line 2).

In the process of breeding inbred lines for viability, there is almost complete repayment of inbred depression in the later generations of inbreeding, the increase in the yield of inbred lines strictly coincides with the increase in the yield of top and bottom crosses obtained from them, and the formation of combinational ability basically coincides with the test of inbred lines in hybrids practiced by breeders after three inbred generations.

In V.A. Strunnikov's experiments on mulberry silkworms, the excess of heterosis in hybrids, one of whose parents was one of the selected inbred lines, is 15-20% or more. This means that the effect of heterosis

increases by almost 2 times compared to the heterosis of conventional hybrids.

Confirmation of the concept of the formation of combinational ability according to V.A. Strunnikov [2], was reflected in the study of I.Z. Kaidanov [3, 4, 5] on the genetics of sexual behavior of drosophila. He created highly inbred lines with increased and decreased viability, which in later inbred generations reached the initial level.

Taking into account possible outbreaks of heterosis in silkworm hybrids during inbred crosses, we set

out to create inbred lines with increased productivity based on large-window breeds.

Material and methods

Taking into account possible outbreaks of heterosis in silkworm hybrids during inbred crosses, we set out to create inbred lines with increased productivity based on large-window breeds. As part of the research of previous years, four inbred lines F-1, F-2, F-3, and F-4 with plus and minus selection for caterpillar viability were obtained from large-window breeding lines L-51 and L-48. Their biological indicators are shown in Table1.

Table 1.

Biological indicators of inbred lines by inbreeding generations

Lines	Generations of inbreeding	Silkworm vitality, %	Cocoon weight, g	Shell weight, mg	Shell ratio, %
		$X^* \pm S^2x^*$	$X^* \pm S^2x^*$	$X^* \pm S^2x^*$	$X^* \pm S^2x^*$
F-1 (increased viability)	J4	66,8±2,8	1,65±0,03	384±8,5	23,4±0,2
	J5	85,5±2,9	2,06±0,03	514±7,5	25,0±0,23
	J6	78,4±3,04	1,79±0,02	419±7,9	23,5±0,3
F-2 (decreased viability)	J4	60,9±4,4	1,73±0,03	395±8,9	22,9±0,2
	J5	79,1±4,4	2,07±0,64	513±2,0	24,8±0,3
	J6	80,3±3,6	1,80±0,03	419±8,9	23,4±0,2
Line-51 (Control)		82,5±1,8	2,03±0,03	522±6,8	25,9±0,1
F-3 (increased viability)	J4	54,0±3,9	1,72±0,03	377±8,4	22,1±0,3
	J5	89,1±2,5	2,03±0,07	487±2,1	24,0±0,3
	J6	82,4±3,4	1,90±0,03	420±8,9	22,2±0,3
F-4 (decreased viability)	J4	53,1±3,5	1,72±0,04	405±12,4	23,8±0,03
	J5	78,6±3,0	1,96±0,03	485±9,1	24,7±0,2
	J6	75,5±3,3	1,76±0,05	405±9,7	23,2±0,4
Line-48 (Control)		84,9±1,9	2,11±0,03	521±12,5	25,1±0,2

Our studies have shown that at the level of the sixth inbred generation, the main biological indicators of inbred lines have almost reached the control level, although inbred depression is still manifested by shell weight (in inbred lines 405-420mg, in the control 522, 521mg) and silkiness (in inbred lines 22,2-23,5%, in the control 25,9 and 25,1%).

Interestingly, there is no difference in productivity indicators between the lines with plus and minus selection. In the F-1 and F-3 lines with selection for increased viability, the cocoon mass indicators of 1,79 g and 1,90 g and the shell mass of 419mg and 420mg, respectively, practically do not differ from the same indicators of the F-2 and F-4 lines with selection for reduced viability of 1,80g and 1,76g, 419mg and 405mg.

To study the combinational value of inbred lines, a series of different crosses were carried out: top crosses (inbred line breeds), bottom crosses (inbred line x breed), and incrosses (inbred line 1 x inbred line 2).

To determine whether the improvement of combinational value occurs simultaneously with the increase in viability, heterosis indices were determined in top crosses, bottom crosses, and incrosses.

The intensity of heterosis was determined by the K.B. Svechin formula:

$$IH = \frac{F \times 100}{P_{av}}$$

where IH is the heterosis index,

F - is an indicator of a trait in hybrids

P_{av} - the average indicator of a sign of two parents.

Since bottom crosses and top crosses are just the forward and reverse directions of the hybrid and, therefore, do not differ from each other in genotypic terms, for the convenience of analysis, we provide data only on bottom crosses.

Results and discussion

We were able to test inbred lines for the strength of heterosis at the level of 4, 5, and 6 inbred generations. Table 2 shows that the effect of heterosis is observed in the viability of caterpillars and the weight of the cocoon.

This is consistent with the data of S.N. Nasriddinova [6] obtained when working with the SANIISH-21 breed, where hybrids exhibit heterosis in viability and cocoon mass, starting from the third inbred generation. According to shell ratio, heterosis is not observed.

Table 2.

The strength of heterosis in the bottom crossed by biological indicators in %% to control

Method of crossing	Generations of in-breeding	Viability of caterpillars, %	Cocoon weight, g	shell weight, mg	Shell ratio, %
F-1 x L-51	4	96,1	115,4	110,0	95,7
	5	103,2	109,5	109,3	99,6
	6	125,1	108,2	108,7	101,2
F-2 x L-51	4	107,0	109,1	107,2	98,7
	5	107,2	105,3	107,2	101,6
	6	131,1	110,3	110,3	100,8
F-3 x -48	4	106,6	107,0	105,5	98,0
	5	102,1	107,1	115,0	106,9
	6	130,6	100,9	98,9	98,0
F-4 x L-48	4	99,4	94,8	91,9	97,2
	5	97,2	106,8	113,9	106,4
	6	117,0	103,8	105,1	102,0

From data obtained by R.K. Kurbanov in 2003-2005, when the first inbred generations were bred, it is known that the outbred offspring originating from the first inbred generation has the same indicators as the outgoing breeds-the second crossing partner.

Starting from the second generation, they increase by 1-2%, the third by 3-15% and are kept at about the

same level in the 4th and 5th generations, and in the 6th they rise to 17-31%. Such results can be considered convincing and quite clearly reveal the process of the formation of combinational ability. The results of the cross test are shown in Table 3.

Table 3.

The strength of heterosis in sun crosses by biological characteristics in %% to control

Method of crossing	Generations	Viability of caterpillars, %	Cocoon weight, g	Shell weight, mg	Shell ratio, %
F-1 x L-51	4	101,2	101,4	102,9	100,1
	5	120,8	111,1	116,2	104,7
	6	136,2	111,5	110,7	99,6
F-2 x L-51	4	83,6	101,4	99,2	97,2
	5	112,1	107,2	118,1	109,9
	6	125,3	106,5	105,8	102,9
F-3 x L-48	4	108,1	105,0	99,2	94,3
	5	119,7	108,7	116,0	106,6
	6	124,0	102,0	108,7	104,9
F-4 x L-48	4	93,7	115,0	116,0	100,4
	5	121,6	108,7	114,0	104,9
	6	127,6	112,1	114,9	102,4

It can be seen that in hybrids originating from different inbred lines in the direction of selection, biological indicators are higher than in the original breeds. Moreover, the strength of heterosis in the viability of caterpillars increases with an increase in the degree of inbreeding of breeding material by up to 36%. This confirms the conclusion about the formation of combinational ability in inbreeding, combined with the selection of viability.

We also investigated the properties of the cocoon thread. The results of technological tests of bottom

crosses and incrosses are shown in Table 4. The indicators of the yield of raw silk, silk products, and the metric number of the cocoon thread are of the greatest interest to us. There is no significant difference between all the crosses for the first two of these indicators. But the metric numbers of incrosses exceed the metric numbers of bottom crosses. In our case, incrosses are hybrids between inbred lines, selected for reduced (F-2, F-4) and increased (F-1, F-3) viability. Crosses between them led to heterosis by the metric number of the cocoon thread.

Table 4.

Results of technological tests of bottom crosses and crosses by inbreeding generation

Hybrids	Generations	Exit, %		Metric number	LCUCTh, m*	Total length of the thread, m
		Raw Silk	Silk Products			
F-1 x Line 51	4	35,36	48,92	2092	733	908
	5	42,23	50,06	2676	1175	1175
	6	41,80	50,55	3343	1129	1945
F-2 x Line 51	4	35,82	51,52	2532	925	992
	5	35,67	51,50	2674	942	967
	6	43,78	50,36	2709	1068	1291
F-3 x Line 48	4	36,91	51,36	2551	950	950
	5	35,31	50,40	3236	1154	1154
	6	36,91	51,36	2551	950	950
F-4 x Line 48	4	45,86	54,63	2645	1125	1216
	5	35,55	50,26	2801	900	975
	6	41,92	50,09	3057	1099	1275
F-1 x F-2	4	39,11	51,90	2967	783	967
	5	36,62	50,90	2899	900	975
	6	39,11	51,90	2967	783	967
F-2 x F-1	4	34,33	50,33	3003	750	750
	5	37,43	52,55	3378	992	1175
	6	41,54	51,10	2663	965	1235
F-3 x F-4	4	42,70	52,99	2875	863	1083
	5	40,00	50,72	2755	750	1035
	6	41,81	50,76	3170	1018	1415
F-4 x F-3	4	42,66	51,62	2915	975	1300
	5	43,72	52,03	3378	1000	1225
	6	42,51	51,54	2936	983	1317
Line 48 (Cont.)		39,89	53,97	2924	708	1083
Line 51 (Cont.)		31,96	52,03	2564	420	930

Note* The length of the continuously unwound (without breakage) cocoon thread

The pattern that we noted by biological signs is also manifested by technological ones – the increase in the metric number of the cocoon thread coincides with an increase in the degree of inbreeding of the lines F-1, F-2, F-3, F-4 in almost all crosses. Obviously, the breeding of inbred lines with the use of selection for increased and decreased viability of caterpillars and their use in hybridization can lead to the manifestation of heterosis and the quality of silk thread.

Conclusions

In general, the analysis of inbred lines for the best combinational ability by creating top crosses, bottom crosses and incrosses showed that all crosses exhibit heterosis.

The increasing effect of heterosis of top crosses, bottom crosses, and incrosses originating from inbred lines, starting from J4 to J6, indicates the constant formation of high combinational ability as the effect of breeding increases on increased and decreased viability of caterpillars in large-window breeding lines Line 48 and Line 51.

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